

Research Article

New combinations in *Ceropegia* (Apocynaceae, Asclepiadoideae, Ceropegieae)

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Abstract: Recent phylogenetic studies and reconstructions (Bruyns et al., 2017) included *Boucerosia* Wight & Arn., *Brachystelma* R.Br., *Crenulluma* Plowes, *Desmidorchis* Ehrenb., *Monolluma* Plowes, *Sulcolluma* Plowes and *Stapelia* L. under the genus *Ceropegia* L. Following the current circumscription and systematics of the genus *Ceropegia* L., nine new combinations and a new name are proposed here under it.

Keywords: *Boucerosia*, *Brachystelma*, *Crenulluma*, Endemic, India, Namibia, Oman, Saudi Arabia, *Stapelia*, *Sulcolluma*

Introduction

The revised taxonomy of the genus *Ceropegia* L. (family Apocynaceae, subfamily Asclepiadoideae, tribe Ceropegieae, subtribe Stapeliinae), based on recent phylogenetic reconstructions (Bruyns et al., 2015 & 2017) included *Boucerosia* Wight & Arn., *Brachystelma* R.Br., *Crenulluma* Plowes, *Desmidorchis* Ehrenb., *Monolluma* Plowes, *Sulcolluma* Plowes and *Stapelia* L. under it. Therefore, based on the current, stable and wider circumscription of *Ceropegia* (Bruyns et al., 2015 & 2017), nine new combinations and a new name are required for 10 species, which are made here.

Nomenclature

Ceropegia bilobata (Sadas. & K.Prasad), R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Brachystelma bilobatum* Sadas. & K.Prasad, Taxon. Rev. Gen. Brachystelma 83. 2020 (July 2020).

Holotype: India, Telangana, Nagarkurnool district, Nagarjunasagar Tiger Reserve, Ap papur, 18 July 2015, *B. Sadasivaiah 2081* (SKU); isotype BSID.

= *Brachystelma telanganense* Rasingam & J.Swamy, *Rheedea* 30(3): 380. 2020 (September 2020).

Holotype: India, Telangana, Mahbubnagar district, Mallayalodhi, 16°18'19.411" N, 78°43'23.72" E, 780 m, 20 April 2018, *L. Rasingam & J. Swamy 8023* (CAL); isotype BSID.

Distribution: Endemic to Telangana state (Mahbubnagar district and Nagarkurnool district), India.

Ceropegia bruynsii R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Stapelia remota* R.A.Dyer, *Bothalia* 12(4): 632. 1979. *Gonostemon remotus* (Dyer) P.V.Heath; *Calyx* 1(1): 18. 1992.

Holotype: Namibia, Kaokoveld, Baynes Mountains, overlooking Kunene River Valley, 1976, *P. Steenkamp 57257* (PRE0730982-0!).

Distribution: Endemic to Republic of Namibia.

Etymology: The species is named after Peter Vincent Bruyns, South African Botanist for his valuable contributions on the genus *Ceropegia*.

Notes: The species epithet *remota* is preoccupied in the genus *Ceropegia* [*Ceropegia remota* (R.A.Dyer) Bruyns (2017: 435)], therefore, a new name is herein proposed.

Ceropegia collenetteae (Plowes) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Crenulluma collenetteae* Plowes, *CactusWorld* 32(4): 295. 2014.

Holotype: Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Summit of Jabal Waggas, c 100 km Southwest of Al Madinah, *I.S. Collenette 5960* (E); isotype (SRGH).

Distribution: Endemic to Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Ceropegia densiflora (K.Prasad, P.Sudheshna & A.M.Reddy), R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Brachystelma densiflorum* K.Prasad, P.Sudheshna & A.M.Reddy, *Taxon. Rev. Gen. Brachystelma* 24. 2020.

Holotype: India, Andhra Pradesh, Sri Potti Sriramulu Nellore district, Veligonda hills, way to Seetharamapuram, 358 m, 10 June 2017, *K. Prasad & P. Sudheshna 5212* (CAL0000033974!); isotype BSID.

Distribution: Endemic to Andhra Pradesh state (Sri Potti Sriramulu Nellore district), India.

Ceropegia kadapensis (M.Sridhar Reddy, C.Ankalaih, T.Mastan, C.V.Ramana, K.Prasad & Venu), R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Brachystelma kadapense* M.Sridhar Reddy, C.Ankalaih, T.Mastan, C.V.Ramana, K.Prasad & Venu, Taxon. Rev. Gen. Brachystelma 86. 2020.

Holotype: India, Andhra Pradesh, YSR (formerly Kadapa) district, Guvvalcheruvu reserve forest, 14°19'0.1" N, 78°45'45.8" E, 478 m, 22 April 2015, C. Ankalaih, T. Mastan & M. Sridhar Reddy 5252 (CAL); isotype BSID.

Distribution: Endemic to Andhra Pradesh state (YSR district), India.

Ceropegia mirbatensis (T.A.McCoy), R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sulcolluma mirbatensis* T.A.McCoy, Cact. Succ. J. (Los Angeles) 84(2): 103. 2012.

Holotype: Sultanate of Oman, Dhofar Governorate, on granites at the base of Jebel Samhan, c 8 km N/NE of Mirbat, 17.04° N, 54.72° E, 20 m, 25 September 2011, T.A. McCoy 3862 (FT).

Distribution: Endemic to Sultanate of Oman (Dhofar Governorate).

Ceropegia penduliflora (Frandsen & Aditya), R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Boucerosia penduliflora* Frandsen & Aditya, Asklepios 126: 11. 2020.

Holotype: India, Odisha, Balasore district, Nilagiri Hills, 200 m, S. Aditya SA 30-099 M (PRE).

Distribution: Endemic to Odisha state (Balasore district), India.

Ceropegia ramaswamii (K.Prasad & Venu), R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Brachystelma ramaswamii* K.Prasad & Venu, Taxon. Rev. Gen. Brachystelma 66. 2020.

Holotype: India, Andhra Pradesh, Nellore district, Veligonda hills, Mullemkonda, c 250 m, 27 July 1914, M.S. Ramaswami 1320 (CAL).

Distribution: Endemic to Andhra Pradesh state (Nellore district), India.

Ceropegia reflexicorollinum (K.Prasad, P.Sudheshna & A.M.Reddy) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Brachystelma reflexicorollinum* K.Prasad, P.Sudheshna & A.M.Reddy, Taxon. Rev. Gen. Brachystelma 37. 2020.

Holotype: India, Andhra Pradesh, YSR (formerly Kadapa) district, near Porumamilla, way to Jothi, 15°2'40" N, 78°48'41" E 356 m, 12 June 2017, K. Prasad & P. Sudeshna 5213 (BSID).

Distribution: Endemic to Andhra Pradesh state (YSR district), India.

Ceropegia tumakurensis (Gundappa, Sringesw., Vishw. & Venu) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Brachystelma tumakurense* Gundappa, Sringesw., Vishw. & Venu, *Rheedea* 31(2): 48. 2021.

Holotype: India, Karnataka, Tumakuru district, Devarayanadurga, near Namada chilume, 700 m, 30 July 2017, *B.V. Gundappa & V. Bhaskar 2546* (UASB); isotype BSI.

Distribution: Endemic to Karnataka state (Tumakuru district), India.

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